

The *Bradyrhizobium diazoefficiens* two-component system NtrYX has a key role in symbiotic nitrogen fixation of soybean plants and *cbb*₃ oxidase expression in bacteroids

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Abstract

Aims

Bradyrhizobium diazoefficiens is a soil bacterium capable of establishing nitrogen-fixing symbiosis with soybean plants, an important crop for food production worldwide. This interaction is under the control of several regulatory factors that affect the bacterial efficiency to nodulate legume plants and fix nitrogen within root nodules. To date, the function of the NtrYX two-component system in *B. diazoefficiens* remains unclear. In this work, we investigated the role of NtrY in the symbiotic interaction of *B. diazoefficiens* with soybean plants.

Methods

We constructed a non-polar mutant of the sensor protein NtrY of the system, and then analysed the symbiosis of this mutant with soybean plants.

Results

We found that the *ntrY* mutant was defective in plant dry weight, nitrogen content and nitrogenase activity. Haem c-staining of *cbb*₃ oxidase components showed a clear reduction in the expression of this terminal oxidase in *ntrY* bacteroids with respect to wild type bacteroids. Such defect in *cbb*₃ expression correlated with a decreased respiratory capacity of the bacteroids produced by the *ntrY* mutant.

Conclusions

These results suggest that the role of *B. diazoefficiens* NtrYX in symbiotic nitrogen fixation might be a consequence of its involvement in *cbb*₃ oxidase expression in bacteroids.

Keywords: Brady rhizobium diazoefficiens · NtrYXtwocomponent · regulatory system · Soybean nodulation · Nitrogen fixation · Cytochrome cbb3 oxidase

Introduction

The atmospheric dinitrogen (N₂)-fixing symbiosis between soil rhizobia and legume plants is a beneficial environmental process that mitigates nitrogen extraction from the soils by plant consumption, thereby allowing to reduce the use of chemical fertilizers to restore fertility (Panzieri et al. [2000](#); Patriarca et al. [2004](#)). This symbiosis is a main contributor to sustainable agriculture and constitutes a key step in the biogeochemical nitrogen cycle. Rhizobia-legume interaction initiates in the soil with a specific signal exchange between both symbiotic partners. Then rhizobia invade the growing roots, in which they form new organs called root nodules. Once into the nodule, rhizobia undergo a differentiation process whereby they are converted into bacteroids, which are able to fix N₂ in a microaerophilic atmosphere (Gage [2004](#); Patriarca et al. [2004](#)). Bacteroids reduce N₂ to ammonia (NH₄⁺), which is supplied to the host plant, providing carbon compounds to the bacteroids (reviewed by Graham and Vance [2003](#); Udvardi and Poole [2013](#)).

The reduction of N₂ to NH₄⁺ is carried out by nitrogenase, a multienzyme complex produced by the bacteroids (Hu and Ribbe [2016](#); Lee et al. [2014](#)). This enzyme is a highly oxygen (O₂)-sensitive protein being denatured irreversibly by O₂ (Shah and Brill [1977](#)). To achieve a low O₂ concentration in the bacteroids (3 to 30 nM), the nodule cortex acts as a diffusion barrier, limiting O₂ permeability (Minchin et al. [2008](#)). Then, the plant O₂-carrier leghaemoglobin (Lb), which is present in infected cells, transports O₂ efficiently to the bacteroids (Downie [2005](#)). In order to use efficiently the low O₂ levels, N₂-fixing bacteroids induce high-affinity oxidases responsible for maintaining an effective electron transport chain, necessary to produce the high demand of energy required for nitrogenase activity (at least 16 mol ATP/mol N₂ reduced). This is the case of the cytochrome *cbb*₃ oxidase encoded by the *fixNOQP* operon, which has been reported to be required for symbiotic nitrogen fixation (Delgado et al. [1998](#)). The ability of rhizobia to carry out an efficient N₂ fixation depends on many regulatory factors, including two-component systems (TCSs). Among them, NtrYX was first identified in *Azorhizobium caulinodans* as being involved in symbiotic nodulation of *Sesbania rostrata* and in free-living nitrogen metabolism (Pawlowski et al. [1991](#)). The sensor histidine kinase (HK) NtrY activates the response regulator (RR) protein NtrX, which in turns binds to promoter regions and modulates gene expression. In α -proteobacteria, this system is generally located downstream the *nifR3ntrBC* operon and presents a considerable homology with NtrBC. Sequence analysis predicts that unlike NtrB, which is cytoplasmic, NtrY is a membrane-associated sensor protein. In *Azospirillum brasilense*, NtrYX regulates nitrate metabolism as well as *nif* genes expression (Ishida et al. [2002](#)). In *Sinorhizobium (Ensifer) meliloti*, NtrX is involved in the regulation of motility, succinoglycan synthesis and

symbiosis with alfalfa, whereas NtrY is dispensable since an *ntrY* mutant behaves like the wild type (WT) (Wang et al. [2013](#)). By contrast, it has been recently reported that NtrYX from *E. meliloti* GR4 influences root colonization and competition for nodule occupancy in alfalfa plants; however, it is not essential for symbiotic nitrogen fixation (Calatrava-Morales et al. [2017](#)). In *Rhizobium tropici*, Nogales et al. ([2002](#)) found that *ntrY* is involved in saline tolerance, whereas mutants in this sensor are inefficient for nodulation of *Phaseolus vulgaris* plants. Recent studies have shown that this TCS is involved in the assimilation of different nitrogen sources in β -proteobacteria like *Ehrlichia chaffeensis* and *Herbaspirillum seropedicae* (Bonato et al. [2016](#); Cheng et al. [2014](#)).

In *Bradyrhizobium diazoefficiens*, the root nodule symbiont of soybean, two hierarchically organized regulatory cascades (RegSR-NifA and FixLJ-FixK₂) control the expression of nitrogen fixation genes (*nif* and *fix*) and genes required for life under microoxic conditions (*fixNOQP* among others), respectively (Dixon and Kahn [2004](#); Fischer [1994](#); Sciotti et al. [2003](#)). FixLJ is a classical TCS that senses and responds to O₂. When the O₂ concentration decreases ($\leq 5\%$ v/v), the sensor protein FixL is autophosphorylated and transfers the phosphoryl group to the FixJ protein, which activates *fixK₂* expression. In turn, the Crp/Fnr-like transcriptional regulator FixK₂ activates the expression of genes involved in microaerobic respiration, particularly *fixNOQP* genes encoding cytochrome *cbb₃* oxidase (Mesa et al. [2005](#), [2008](#)). In the RegSR-NifA cascade, RegSR belongs to the redox-responsive TCS family present in Proteobacteria. The expression of the *fixR-nifA* operon is induced by RegR under all O₂ conditions (Bauer et al. [1998](#)). Upon a switch to very low O₂ conditions ($\leq 0.5\%$ v/v) and in concert with RNA polymerase σ^{54} factor (RpoN), NifA enhances its own synthesis and activates *nif* and *fix* genes expression, both involved in N₂-fixation.

B. diazoefficiens USDA 110 also possesses homologous genes to *ntrYX* from *A. caulinodans* downstream from the *nifR3ntrBC* genes. It has been recently reported that *B. diazoefficiens* NtrC is required for the expression of the *nasC* and *nirA* genes involved in free-living nitrate assimilation, and that RpoN is also involved in this regulation (López et al. [2017](#)). However, the role of the NtrYX system from *B. diazoefficiens* is not known yet. In this work, we constructed an *ntrY* mutant and investigated its involvement in the symbiotic interaction with soybean plants.

Materials and methods

Bacterial strains, plasmids, primers and growth conditions

Bacterial strains and plasmids used in this study are listed in Table [1](#). Table [S1](#) summarizes the primers used in this work. Bacteria were routinely grown at 28 °C in yeast-extract-mannitol medium (YEM) (Vincent [1974](#)) and Evans defined medium (Evans et al. [1970](#)) with 10 g mannitol l⁻¹ as the C-source and 20 mM NH₄Cl as the N-source. They

were cultured on a rotary shaker at 28 °C and 180 rpm in Erlenmeyer flasks containing a volume of the medium to be assayed equal to 20% of the flask capacity.

Table 1 Bacterial strains and plasmids used in this study

	Genotype and phenotype	Reference
Strains		
<i>E. coli</i>		
DH5α	<i>supE44 ΔlacU169 (ϕ80 lacZ ΔM15) hsdR17 recA1 endA1 gyrA96 thi-1 relA1</i>	Bethesda Research Laboratories
S17-1	<i>Tra⁺, recA pro thi hsdR chr::RP4-2</i>	Simon et al. 1983
<i>B. diazoefficiens</i>		
USDA 110	Wild-type strain, Cm ^r	US Department of Agriculture, Beltsville, MD, USA
LP4489	USDA 110 Δ <i>ntrY</i>	This work
Plasmids		
pK18mobSacB	Rhizobial suicide vector, Km ^r , Mob ⁺ , SacB ⁺	Schäfer et al. 1994
pVH4489	pK18mob2:: <i>ntrY</i>	This work

Oxygen consumption, haem staining and plant assays were assessed in a single colony of each *B. diazoefficiens* strain grown in peptone–salt–yeast–extract (PSY) medium supplemented with 0.1% (w/v) L-arabinose (Regensburger and Hennecke [1983](#)) at 28 °C and 180 rpm. Strains were then diluted in flasks containing YEM medium and maintained at 28 °C in aerobic or microaerobic conditions, as required for each experiment. The microaerobic condition was kept by injecting 2% O₂ in the gas atmosphere every 12 h.

For plant experiments, rhizobia strains were grown in YEM medium. Cultures were diluted in Evans minimal medium without its N-source. After 3–4 days, cultures were diluted in modified N-free Fåhræus plant nutrient solution (Lodeiro et al. [2000](#)) in order to inoculate ca. 10⁶ CFU.ml⁻¹ over each soybean seed.

Escherichia coli strains were cultured in Luria–Bertani (LB) medium (Miller [1972](#)) at 37 °C. Kanamycin was added at 25 µg.ml⁻¹ when needed.

Chloramphenicol (20 µg. ml⁻¹) and/or kanamycin (200 µg. ml⁻¹) were added to *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110 cultures or plates when needed.

Bioinformatics methods

Promoter prediction was carried out using the BDGP Neural Network Promoter Prediction program (Reese [2001](#)). All the oligonucleotides were designed with Primer BLAST (Ye et al. [2012](#)). The Pfam program at EMBL-EBI online server (<http://pfam.xfam.org>) was used to perform the protein domain analysis.

Construction of the *B. diazoefficiens ntrY* mutant

Cloning procedures were performed as described by Sambrook and Russell ([2001](#)). Genomic DNA was isolated using the Wizard Genomic DNA purification Kit (Promega) and digestions were carried out with FastDigest (Fermentas) or Promega enzymes as

necessary, following the manufacturer's instructions. Custom oligonucleotide primers were supplied by Genbiotech SRL (Buenos Aires, Argentina). Taq DNA polymerase (Embiotec, Buenos Aires, Argentina) or Pfx polymerase (Invitrogen) were used to perform polymerase-chain reactions (PCR).

The in-frame, non-polar deletion mutation was obtained following the cross-over PCR cloning procedure described by Sukdeo and Charles (2003). Gene-target flanking DNA fragments were amplified by PCR using specific primers (Table S1), one of each pair with a short synthetic tail (21 pb) that maintains the translational reading frame. Thus, primers ntrY5' -Eco FW and ntrY5' RV for PCR 1 and ntrY3' FW and ntrY3' -PstI RV for PCR 2 were designed for the amplification of upstream (340 bp) and downstream (422 bp) fragments of *ntrY* (PCR 1 and PCR 2 according to the methods in the references cited). These two first PCR reactions were carried out using *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110 genomic DNA as template and generated fragments with complementary ends due to the synthetic short sequences added. The third PCR reaction with outside primers (ntrY5' -Eco FW and ntrY3' -PstI RV) allowed us to obtain the target gene (742 bp) with the desired deletion without reading-frame change. This PCR product replaces an internal 2286-bp fragment of the 2547-bp coding sequence of *ntrY*. Finally, the 742 bp construct was cloned into pK18mobsacB vector (Schäfer et al. 1994) and transferred by electroporation to *E. coli* DH5 α by using a Gene Pulser system (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA) at 1.5 V, 25 μ F and 200 Ω in a 0.1-cm-gap-width electroporation cuvette (Simon et al. 1983). Clones were selected in LB medium supplemented with X-gal and kanamycin 25 μ g.ml⁻¹. Positive clones were confirmed by PCR and sequencing (Macrogen Inc., Korea). Plasmids with the correct construction were isolated using Accuprep Plasmid MiniPrep DNA Extraction Kit (Bioneer) and transferred to *E. coli* S-17 electrocompetent cells for biparental mating to *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110. The transconjugants obtained (simple recombinants) were screened as kanamycin-resistant and confirmed by PCR. Positive clones were grown in PSY medium supplemented with 0.1% arabinose and plated on YEM supplemented with 10% sucrose in order to generate double recombination events. The resulting clones were then plated on YEM and YEM-kanamycin replicates. Kanamycin-sensitive clones were checked for the correct recombination at the target gene using both PCR with 4489check FW/RV primers (Table S1) and sequencing with cheq-ntrY FW/RV primers (Table S1) (Macrogen Inc., Korea). One of the double-recombinant clones that resulted in an in-frame non-polar *ntrY* gene deletion (Δ *ntrY*) was named as LP4489, and experiments were accordingly carried out with that strain.

RNA extraction and reverse transcription PCR (RT-PCR)

Total RNA was extracted following the technique described by Mongiardini et al. (2017) with some modifications. Essentially, 30 ml of *B. diazoefficiens* cultures grown in Evans medium to an OD₅₀₀ of about 2.3 were harvested and disrupted with lysozyme in Tris-EDTA buffer, pH 8.0, for 30 min at 37 °C. Total RNA was extracted with TRIzol (Life

Technologies, Buenos Aires, Argentina) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The quality and quantity of RNA were determined with a NanoDrop spectrophotometer (NanoDrop Technologies, Wilmington, DE). Aliquots (0.125 µg) were treated with DNase I for 30 min at 37 °C, and cDNA was synthesized with Moloney murine leukemia virus reverse transcriptase (Life Technologies) by using random hexamer primers following the manufacturer's instructions. To check the quality of the cDNA preparation, PCRs were performed with primer pairs *relA* FW/RV (Pérez-Giménez et al. 2009; Table S1) as described previously (Quelas et al. 2010). The absence of contaminating DNA was demonstrated by the lack of PCR amplification in an RNA sample that was not subjected to RT-PCR. Primers for the housekeeping gene *sigA* were used as positive control (Hauser et al. 2006).

To determine the operon structure, three RT-PCRs were performed with the appropriate cDNAs for each fragment. Accordingly, two reactions amplified fragments of the coding sequence of each contiguous gene (positive control), while the third amplified a fragment encompassing the intergenic region between the target genes (Redondo-Nieto et al. 2008). In addition, each RT-PCR reaction had a negative control without reverse transcriptase, in which no transcripts were detected, and a positive control using genomic DNA as template.

Analysis of *fixN* gene expression by real-time (q) RT-PCR

The expression of *fixN* was analyzed by qRT-PCR using an iQTM5 Optical System (Bio-Rad, CA, USA). *B. diazoefficiens* WT and the *ntrY* mutant strain were grown in YEM medium under 2% O₂ for 48 h. Total RNA was isolated using the hot phenol extraction procedure described previously (Babst et al. 1996). First strand cDNA synthesis was performed using SuperScript II reverse transcriptase (Invitrogen) according to the supplier's guidelines. Each PCR reaction contained 9.5 µl of iQTM SYBR Green Supermix (Bio-Rad), 2 µM (final concentration) of individual primers (*fixN*_qRT_For / *fixN*_qRT_Rev, Torres et al. 2014; Table S1) and appropriate dilutions of different cDNA samples in a total volume of 19 µl. Reactions were run in triplicate. Melting curves were generated to verify the specificity of the amplification. Relative changes in gene expression were calculated as described by Pfaffl (2001). The expression of the *napA*, the gene encoding the catalytic subunit of the periplasmic nitrate reductase (Nap), was used as reference for normalization (primers *napA*_qRT_For/ *napA*_qRT_Rev; Table S1).

Plant growth conditions

Soybean seeds (*Glycine max*, Don Mario 4800) were surface-sterilized and germinated as previously described by Quelas et al. (2013). Germinated seeds were sown in sterile sand:perlite (3:2) mixture pots containing modified N-free Fåhraeus plant nutrient solution (Lodeiro et al. 2000). Plants were grown in controlled environment chambers (19/25 °C night/day temperature, 16-h light/8-h dark photoperiod;

400 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ photosynthetic photon flux (PPF); 60–70% relative humidity). Plant pots were irrigated with sterile distilled water every two days and provided one watering with Fåhraeus solution every week.

Symbiotic nitrogen fixation assays

Plant growth parameters were assessed in 25- and/or 50-day-old-plants. Shoots or nodules from each plant were cut and dried at 60 °C to a constant weight. Some of these nodules were separated for microscopy exploration. Total nitrogen [N] was measured as described by Torres et al. (2013). The statistical analysis of shoot dry weight (SDWP), nodule number (NNP) and nodule dry weight (NDWP) per plant as well as [N] was performed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), with significance set at $p < 0.01$.

Nitrogenase activity was measured with the acetylene reduction assay (ARA) (Hardy et al. 1968; Hardy et al. 1973). Briefly, 21-day-old plants were carefully cleaned of their growing substrate, trying not to damage or detach nodules. Then, the roots were placed into a glass bottle with a few milliliters of water and sealed with a septum, leaving the shoot and aerial part out. Ten percent of the gas atmosphere in the bottle was replaced by a pure acetylene injection through the septum. Finally, samples from the bottle gas atmosphere were taken every 2 h and the ethylene content was measured by chromatography using an HP 4890D gas chromatograph (Agilent Technologies, S.L., Madrid; Spain) equipped with a flame ionization detector.

Nodule functionality was estimated by analysing the Lb content of nodules as described by Talbi et al. (2012), following the method previously described by LaRue and Child (1979). Briefly, fresh nodules were ground with extraction buffer and the homogenate was centrifuged at 12,000 g at 4 °C for 20 min. Once separated, the clear supernatant was mixed with saturated oxalic acid in screw-capped tubes and autoclaved for 30 min at 120 °C. Once at room temperature, the fluorescence of the solution was measured using a Shimadzu spectrophotofluorometer (Shimadzu Scientific Instruments, Kyoto, Japan) with excitation and emission wavelengths of 405 nm and 650 nm, respectively. The haem protein content was proportional to the difference in fluorescence between heated and unheated samples.

Microscopy

Twenty-five-day-old nodules were observed and micrographed with an FDC480 digital camera coupled to an MZ FLIII stereomicroscope device (Leica Microsystems). Nodules were excised (each one transversally cut in halves), collected and fixed in 2% (v/v) glutaraldehyde, and prepared for transmission electron microscopy as previously described by Quelas et al. (2010). Microscope observations and micrograph acquisitions were performed as previously described (Quelas et al. 2013). For light microscopy, 2- μm -thick glutaraldehyde-fixed sections of nodules were treated according

to Quelas et al. (2013). Electron microscopy samples were observed and micrographed in an Eclipse E200 microscope with a camera coupled to the device (Nikon).

Determination of bacterial respiratory capacity

Oxygen uptake was determined as described previously (Torres et al. 2013). Briefly, cultures grown aerobically or microaerobically in YEM medium for 48 h were harvested and cells were washed and resuspended in 25 mmol·l⁻¹ potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0). Bacteroids were isolated as described previously (Mesa et al. 2004) and resuspended in the same buffer.

Oxygen uptake was measured after addition of 2 mmol·l⁻¹ N,N,N',N'-tetramethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine (TMPD) and 4 mmol·l⁻¹ sodium ascorbate to the cellular suspension (about 0.40 mg protein per ml) using a Clark-type oxygen electrode (Hansatech, Norkfolk, UK). Then, TMPD-dependent oxygen consumption rate was calculated for each determination by measuring the time taken to consume the oxygen present and plotted in the Oxygraph Plus software coupled to the electrode. Data were statistically analysed with Student *t* test or Tukey test ($p < 0.01$).

Detection of bacterial cytochromes by haem c-staining

For free-living lifestyle, cells grown microaerobically in YEM medium were harvested and disrupted, and membranes separated as described by Torres et al. (2013). Bacteroids were isolated from soybean nodules as previously described (Mesa et al. 2004). Similar procedures were used to separate the membranes. Briefly, WT or mutant strain membrane proteins previously quantified using the Bio-Rad assay were diluted in loading buffer. They were separated at 4 °C by SDS-12% polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE). Once transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane, proteins were stained for haem-dependent peroxidase activity as described by Vargas et al. (1993), using the SuperSignal chemiluminescence detection kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Pierce, IL, USA). When necessary, relative intensities of protein bands were determined using ImageJ 1.48v software analysis.

Analytical methods

The protein concentration was measured using the Bio-Rad kit assay (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Richmond, CA) against a standard curve prepared with bovine-serum-albumin.

Protein isolation, separation and analysis

The differential proteomes of *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110 and $\Delta ntrY$ mutant strain were studied with protein samples obtained from bacteria grown in Evans medium for five days until exponential growth phase. Rhizobia samples were obtained from three independent cultures per condition, following the technique described by Cogo et al. (2018) for cytoplasmic proteins. Briefly, 150 ml of each culture was centrifuged at 7150 x g,

followed by two washes of the pellets with low-salt washing buffer (3 mM KCl, 1.5 mM KH₂PO₄, 68 mM NaCl, 9 mM NaH₂PO₄). Pellets were then resuspended in 10 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.5 up to an OD_{500 nm} = 25, adding 1 ml of phenyl methyl sulfonyl fluoride in Tris-HCl per ml. Then, the protocol described by Cogo et al. (2018) was applied, including protein separation and analysis and bioinformatics analysis.

Results

Characterization of the *ntrYX* operon in *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110

The *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110 NtrY-NtrX TCS is encoded at blr4489 and blr4490 loci, respectively, located downstream from *nifR3ntrBC* genes and upstream from *hfq-hflX* genes (Fig. 1a). In contrast to other α -proteobacteria, the *trkA* gene is not located within this operon (Carrica et al. 2012; Wang et al. 2013). The contiguous location of *ntrY* and *ntrX*, together with the Blastp predictions and the conserved synteny of gene neighborhoods through within the Rhizobiaceae family are indicative of a functional TCS. Diverse algorithms are able to predict transcriptional units within gene clusters based upon similarities in function and gene expression profiles. Data banks of predicted operons showed that *ntrY-ntrX* are co-transcribed. Thus, the transcriptional architecture of this region was further characterized by RT-PCR to detect the intergenic regions between *ntrB-C* (a), *ntrC-Y* (b) and *ntrY-X* (c) (Fig. 1a, b). As shown in Fig. 1b, RT-PCR from the intergenic region between *ntrC* and *ntrY* resulted in the absence of any cDNA product, suggesting that *nifR3ntrBC* and *ntrYX* clusters were transcribed separately. By contrast, specific cDNA products were obtained for intergenic regions between *ntrY* and *ntrX* and *ntrB* and *ntrC*, suggesting that *B. diazoefficiens ntrYX* as well as *ntrBC* constituted two independent transcriptional units (Fig. 1b). These results are in agreement with previous observations showing the structure of the *ntrY-ntrX* operon in other α -proteobacteria (Carrica et al. 2012; Drepper et al. 2006). On the other hand, data in the literature suggest that the *hfq-hflX* genes, which are contiguous downstream to the *ntrY-ntrX* operon, form a bicistronic operon separately from the contiguous genes (Torres-Quesada et al. 2010). Additionally, Čuklina et al. (2016) determined the presence of a transcription start site upstream to *hfq* in the intergenic region between *ntrYX* and *hfq-hflX* genes in *B. diazoefficiens* (Fig. 1a), suggesting again that those genes are a separate transcriptional unit.

Fig. 1 Transcriptional organization of *B. diazoefficiens* *nifRntrBC* and *ntrYX* gene clusters. **a** Genomic context of *ntrYX* genes of *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110. The positions of the deduced promoters according to bioinformatics prediction (BDGP Neural Network Program Promoter Prediction) are shown above the scheme as black arrows. The dotted black arrow indicates a weak promoter for the *ntrX* gene predicted by Čuklina et al. (2016) and BDGP as well. The positions of the intergenic amplicons according to the RT-PCR strategy are shown below the scheme as black segments numbered a, b and c. **b** RT-PCR products corresponding to the intergenic regions between *ntrB* and *ntrC* (a), *ntrY* and *ntrX* (c) and *ntrC* and *ntrY* genes (b). Total RNA served as the template for cDNA synthesis by using specific primers of the intergenic

regions. Genomic DNA extracted from *B. diazoefficiens* WT was used as positive control. The *sigA* gene was used as constitutive reference gene. Primer sequences are shown in Table [S1](#)

In order to investigate the function of *B. diazoefficiens ntrYX* operon, we constructed an in-frame *ntrY* deletion mutant to prevent any polar effects on *ntrX*, and expecting that this gene would be properly transcribed. The construction strategy to obtain the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant (named LP4489) is schematized in Fig. [S1A](#), whereas the confirmation of the mutant genotype is shown in Fig. [S1B](#). Thus, the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant would be expected to transcribe a shorter *ntrY* gene (282 bp) codifying for a non functional protein according to the domain analysis. Thereby, we observed that *ntrY* expression was affected in the mutant, while *ntrX* was transcribed, even showing a relatively higher expression than that observed in the WT strain (Fig. [2](#)). This finding was somewhat surprising and at the same time different from data of other *ntrY* mutants reported in the literature. Our mutation strategy differed from the one previously used to obtain *ntrY* mutants, which had a polar effect on the *ntrX* gene and showed a significant decrease of the *ntrX* transcript (Calatrava-Morales et al. [2017](#); Wang et al. [2013](#)). Despite the higher levels of *ntrX* transcript in the $\Delta ntrY$ strain (Fig. [2](#)), proteomic in-depth analysis comparing NtrX abundance between the *ntrY* mutant and the WT strain revealed no differences in NtrX protein level (Table [S2](#)). The protein profiles were carried out in the same conditions as the RT-PCR experiments. In addition, we corroborated that proteins contiguous to NtrY-NtrX like NtrB, NtrC, Hfq and HflX were not different between both strains (Table [S2](#)).

Fig. 2 RT-PCR products corresponding to *ntrY* and *ntrX* by using cDNA from *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110 or the *ntrY* mutant and the specific gene primers listed in Table S1. Genomic DNA extracted from *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110 was used as positive control. The *sigA* gene was used as constitutive reference gene

In parallel to the construction of the *ntrY* mutant, we tried to obtain a single *ntrX* deletion mutant as well as a double *ntrYntrX* deletion mutant. However, several attempts to generate them failed, presumably because the deletion of *B. diazoefficiens ntrX* might be lethal, as it has been suggested in other bacteria (Bonato et al. 2016; Calatrava-Morales et al. 2017; Carrica et al. 2012; Gregor et al. 2007; Ishida et al. 2002).

Symbiotic phenotype of the *ntrY* mutant

To investigate the role of NtrYX in the symbiotic interaction with soybean plants, we performed nodulation assays with the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant and WT strains. After 25 days of growth, non-inoculated plants (Fig. 3c, j) were smaller and with yellowish leaves compared with plants inoculated with the WT strain (Fig. 3a, h). Interestingly, the aspect of soybean plants inoculated with the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant was similar to that of uninoculated control plants, since they presented small and with pale green leaves (Fig. 3b, i). These results suggest that plants inoculated with the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant were defective in N_2 -fixation. Furthermore, the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant produced small and white pseudonodules (Fig. 3e, g) compared with those induced by the WT strain (Fig. 3d, f). The $\Delta ntrY$ mutant symbiotic

phenotype described above was also observed in experiments carried out up to 50 days post-inoculation (data not shown).

Fig. 3 Symbiotic phenotype of *B. diazoefficiens* ntrY deletion mutant and wild type USDA 110. Leaves, nodules and plants of soybean inoculated with USDA 110 (**a**, **d**, **f**, **h**) or LP4489 (**b**, **e**, **g**, **i**) strains. **a** to **c** show leaves, and **d** to **g** show pictures of root nodules from 25 day-old plants. **c** corresponds to leaves from non-inoculated plants. **j**, non-inoculated plants

To confirm these observations, a set of physiological parameters including shoot dry weight (SDWP), number of nodules per plant (NNP), nodule dry weight per plant (NDWP), total nitrogen content (N), and leghaemoglobin content (Lb) were measured in plants

inoculated with the WT or $\Delta ntrY$ mutant strains (Table 2). In plants inoculated with the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant, NNP was about 2-fold higher compared with that of plants inoculated with the WT strain. On the contrary, NDWP of plants infected with the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant was significantly lower (about 2.5-fold) compared with that of plants inoculated with the WT (Table 2). The higher NNP induced by the $ntrY$ mutant was possibly related to the fact that these nodules are inefficient, and the need for N at the whole-plant level would affect autoregulatory mechanisms. In fact, plants inoculated with the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant displayed a significant decrease in Lb and ARA compared with those inoculated with the WT strain (94 and 48%, respectively) (Table 2). Such decrease in N_2 -fixation activity was confirmed by the N concentration in plants, about 59% N decrease in $\Delta ntrY$ mutant-inoculated plants as compared with the WT (Table 2).

Table 2 Symbiotic parameters of *Bradyrhizobium diazoefficiens* LP4489 ($\Delta ntrY$ mutant) and the wild type USDA 110

Strain	Symbiotic parameters*					
	NNP	NDWP (mg)	SDW (g plant ⁻¹)	[N] (mg plant ⁻¹)	ARA ($\mu\text{mol ethylene g}^{-1}$ NFW)	Lb (mg g ⁻¹ NFW)
USDA 110	22 ± 3a	90.7 ± 11.5a	1.62 ± 0.11a	13.84 ± 2.45a	235 ± 17a	7.40 ± 0.07a
LP4489 ($\Delta ntrY$)	44 ± 3b	36.6 ± 2.3b	0.41 ± 0.03b	5.68 ± 0.55b	122 ± 19b	0.42 ± 0.03b

Data are expressed as means ± standard error (SE) from at least 15 plants assayed per strain in at least three independent experiments.

Different lower-case letters indicate values that are significantly different as determined by ANOVA-Tukey test ($p < 0.01$)

*(SDWP): Shoot dry weight; [N]: nitrogen content; (NNP): nodules number per plant; (NDWP): nodule dry weight per plant; (NFW): nodule fresh weight; ARA: acetylene reduction activity; Lb: leghaemoglobin content. [N], ARA and Lb were measured in plants grown during 25 days after inoculation; NNP, NDWP and SDWP were measured in 50-day-old plants

Likewise, SDWP after 50 days of growth was significantly decreased in plants inoculated with the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant compared with those infected with the WT (Table 2), and similar to that of noninoculated control plants (0.47 ± 0.03 g plant⁻¹), indicating a severe defect in N_2 -fixation in this mutant.

Electron microscopy analyses showed that the ultrastructure of the nodules produced by the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant differed with respect to the WT nodules (Fig. 4). As shown in Fig. 4, $\Delta ntrY$ nodules displayed multiple vacuoles located in the perinuclear region of infected cells, as well as enlarged cell walls in the outermost cortical cells, resembling symptoms of cellular lysis (Regensburger et al. 1986; Werner et al. 1984). Furthermore, we observed a smaller number of bacteroids per field in nodules occupied by the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant than in WT nodules (3–4 bacteroids per symbiosome; Fig. 4), as usually observed in young determinate nodules (Fedorova et al. 1999).

Fig.4 Transmission electron micrographs of ultrathin cuts of 25-day-old soybean nodules from plants inoculated with *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110 or the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant. Note the vacuolar structures as bright vesicles inside the cytoplasm. Lower case bold letters on the images indicate the features mentioned in the text (**v**, vacuola; **b**, bacteroid; **cw**, cell wall). Scale bars, 2 μ m. A representative micrograph observed from triplicate nodule samples is presented for each strain

Taken together, these results indicate that the mutation produced in the *B. diazoefficiens* *ntrY* gene provoked a clear defect at various levels of the symbiotic N_2 -fixation activity.

Respiratory capacity of the *B. diazoefficiens* $\Delta ntrY$ mutant under free-living and symbiotic conditions

Cytochrome *c*-dependent oxygen consumption capacity was measured in the WT and the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant strains using ascorbate-reduced TMPD as a nonphysiological electron donor. Independently of the strain, TMPD-oxidase activity in free-living bacteria grown aerobically was lower than that measured in cells grown under microaerobic conditions (Table 3). This higher capacity of O_2 consumption under microaerobic conditions compared with aerobically-grown cells was also observed in *E. meliloti* (Torres et al. 2013). One possible explanation could be that high-affinity cytochrome *c* oxidases with greater activity are induced in microaerobic cultures. Likewise, TMPD-oxidase activity levels were significantly lower in the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant as compared with the WT strain in both aerobic (2.5-fold) and microaerobic (1.6-fold) conditions after 48-h growth (Table 3).

Table 3 TMPD-dependent oxygen consumption activity by free- living cells and bacteroids of the wild-type *B. diazoefficiens* USDA 110 and $\Delta ntrY$ mutant (LP4489)

Oxygen consumption (nmoles O_2 .min ⁻¹ .mg ⁻¹ protein)			
Strains	Free-living ^(*)		Bacteroids ^(*)
	Aerobic	Micro-aerobic	
USDA 110	538 ± 72a	1763 ± 11a	455 ± 42a
LP4489 ($\Delta ntrY$)	213 ± 45b	1062 ± 76b	221 ± 24b

Data are expressed as the means with the standard error from at least three replicates assayed per strain and condition at least in triplicate. Different lower-case letters indicates that values are significantly different as determined by ANOVA-Tukey test ($P < 0.01$)

(*)Cells were grown during 48 h in YEM medium under aerobic or micro-oxic conditions and bacteroids were isolated from nodules of 25-day old plants

Oxygen consumption rates of bacteroids isolated from 25-day-old plant nodules and inoculated with USDA 110 or the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant were also determined. Similarly to free-living cell results, TMPD-dependent O_2 consumption activity of $\Delta ntrY$ bacteroids was about 2-fold lower than that of bacteroids produced by WT cells (Table 3). The lower respiratory activity observed in $\Delta ntrY$ bacteroids suggests a disability in providing ATP to the nitrogenase reaction, which would lead to the observed defect in N_2 -fixation.

***cbb*₃ oxidase expression in free-living cells and bacteroids of the *B. diazoefficiens ntrY* mutant**

It is well known that the *cbb*₃-type high affinity oxidase encoded by the *fixNOQP* operon supports microaerobic respiration in endosymbiotic *B. diazoefficiens* bacteroids and is essential for N₂-fixing symbiosis (Preisig et al. [1993](#); Preisig et al. [1996](#)). The FixP and FixO components of *cbb*₃ oxidase are membrane-bound c-type cytochromes with molecular masses of 32 and 28 kDa, respectively (Preisig et al. [1993](#)). The expression of *cbb*₃ oxidase was analysed by performing haem-c staining analyses in both free-living bacteria growing under microaerobic conditions and bacteroids (Fig. [5](#)). Proteins from the WT and the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant membrane fractions were separated by SDS-PAGE, with each lane containing the same amounts of total proteins, and stained for covalently-bound haem proteins. Four stained bands of 32, 28, 25 and 20 kDa were detected in WT membranes (Fig. [5a](#), lane 1). As mentioned above, the 32- and 28-kDa proteins corresponded to the FixP and FixO components of the *cbb*₃-type cytochrome oxidase. As described by Thöny-Meyer et al. ([1989](#)), an additional 28 kDa protein co-migrated with FixO, which corresponded to cytochrome *c*₁. The 25- and 20-kDa proteins had been previously identified as *B. diazoefficiens* NapC (Delgado et al. [2003](#)) and CycM (Bott et al. [1991](#)), respectively.

Fig.5 Haem c-staining SDS-PAGE analysis. Proteins were isolated from membranes of free-living cells incubated microaerobically in YEM medium for 48 h (a) or from bacteroids isolated from nodules of 25-day-old plants inoculated with USDA 110 or the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant (b). Haem-stained c-type cytochromes identified previously are specified in the right margin. Apparent protein molecular masses (in kDa) are shown in the left margin of each image. In a, each lane contains about 60 mg membrane proteins, while in b they contain about 20 mg. Panels beneath each SDS-PAGE gel show Coomassie-blue stained membranes as protein loading control

Similarly to WT cells, four haem-c stained bands were detected in membrane fractions of the *ntrY* mutant (Fig. 5a, lane 2). However, the intensity of the bands corresponding to FixP and FixO/*c*₁ decreased appreciably with respect to those of the WT (Fig. 5a, lanes 1 and 2). In fact, after ImageJ analysis, a relative band intensity reduction was observed (50% for FixP and about 30% for FixO/*c*₁) in the *ntrY* mutant with respect to the WT (Fig. S2A). On the contrary, similar NapC levels were detected in membranes of the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant compared to USDA 110 membranes (Fig. 5a, lanes 1 and 2). In addition to FixP and FixO/*c*₁, the level of CycM was about 50% lower in the *ntrY* mutant than in WT cells (Fig. 5a, lanes 1 and 2; Fig. S2B). These results indicated that NtrY controlled the expression of *cbb*₃-oxidase under microaerobic conditions, and were confirmed by qRT-PCR, since the expression of *fixN* – the gene encoding the catalytic subunit of *cbb*₃ oxidase – was reduced in the *ntrY* mutant (2.65-fold) compared with WT cells. However, no change was detected in the expression of the *napA* gene, which was used as internal constitutive control for *fixN* expression analyses.

Finally, haem-c staining analyses of membrane preparations from bacteroids isolated from nodules of 25-day-old plants inoculated with USDA 110 or the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant were carried out. By contrast to free-living conditions (Fig. 5a), only the 32- and 28-kDa c-type cytochromes corresponding to FixP and FixO/*c*₁ were detected in bacteroids from the WT strain (Fig. 5b, lane 1). Meanwhile, bands corresponding to NapC and CycM were not detected in membranes from WT bacteroids. As shown in Fig. 5b, we did not detect any c-type cytochrome in membranes from *ntrY* bacteroids (Fig. 5b, lane 2). This result could explain the decreased respiratory capacity of the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant as compared with USDA 110 (Table 3).

Discussion

In prokaryotes, TCSs play an important role in signal transduction, allowing bacteria to adapt and respond to diverse environmental stimuli by the expression of specific genes, thereby regulating diverse metabolic processes. Data available in the literature about the role of the NtrYX TCS in the interaction with the host plant are controversial, since they differ depending on the rhizobial species considered. In this work, contrarily to that reported for *E. meliloti* (Wang et al. 2013), we show that NtrY is required for efficient symbiotic N fixation in *B. diazoefficiens*.

We demonstrated that the *ntrY-ntrX* genes in *B. diazoefficiens* were cotranscribed as an operon. As it was expected, *ntrX* was expressed in the $\Delta ntrY$ strain, albeit we have no clear explanation for the observed higher *ntrX* gene expression in the *ntrY* mutant. However, we verified that there was no correlation between the level of the *ntrX* transcript and the abundance of NtrX in the mutant. In fact, in our studies, the NtrX protein was identified as a non-differential protein between both strains, showing the same protein abundance. This observation suggests that there might be another regulation of the NtrX translation that leads to produce the same amount of protein. Similar results have been recently observed in a chromosomally myc-tagged *ntrX* strain of *Caulobacter crescentus*, which presents high levels of the *ntrX* transcript without detection of the NtrXmyc protein (Fernández et al. 2018). Despite these results and considerations, we had difficulty in assessing the functionality of the NtrX protein in the $\Delta ntrY$ strain. It has been shown that NtrY specifically transfers the signal to its response regulator NtrX in *Brucella spp* (Carrica et al. 2012). Notably, a cross-talk response exists between NtrBC and NtrYX systems in *A. brasilense* and *Rhodobacter capsulatus*, in which NtrC can be phosphorylated and activated by NtrB or NtrY (Drepper et al. 2006; Ishida et al. 2002). However, this interaction did not seem to occur in *B. diazoefficiens*. Furthermore, Fernández et al. (2017) demonstrated that in *Brucella*, unphosphorylated NtrX bound to the *ntrYX* promoter (pYX) region with low affinity and regulated its own expression. In this regard, Čuklina et al. (2016) suggested the presence of a transcription start site of the *ntrYX* operon at the end of *ntrC* and another weak site upstream to *ntrX* in *B. diazoefficiens*. In view of our results, we propose that unphosphorylated NtrX could bind to that promoter and activate its own transcription in the *ntrY* mutant. Additionally, although NtrX was present in the mutant, the phenotypic changes observed in $\Delta ntrY$ strain could be probably due to the lack of NtrX protein phosphorylation by its cognate HK, NtrY. We are currently performing further experiments to elucidate the mechanism involved in the transcription regulation of *ntrYX* in *B. diazoefficiens*. Finally, insights gained from characterizing NtrYX activity modulation will be highly relevant to understanding bacterial perception of the host environment.

The ability of rhizobia to carry out an efficient symbiotic N₂-fixation depends on many factors. An essential condition is the capacity to maintain a low concentration of O₂ in the nodule, allowing the nitrogenase enzyme to work. This environment requires the expression of high-affinity oxidases to support respiration and provide ATP to the energy-demanding nitrogenase activity (Delgado et al. 1998). It has been demonstrated that in *Brucella* and *Neisseria*, the sensor kinase NtrY is necessary for adaptation to the O₂-limiting conditions that are present in their replicative niche. However, the involvement of NtrYX in the adaptation of rhizobia to microaerobic respiration has not been reported so far. A significantly low rate of O₂ consumption was observed in the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant both under aerobic and microaerobic conditions. These results indicate that *B. diazoefficiens* NtrY is involved in controlling O₂ respiration, as reported

for *Brucella* (Carrica et al. [2013](#)). However, and consistent with that observed in *Brucella* sp. (Carrica et al. [2013](#)), the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant grew like the WT strain under microaerobic free-living conditions (data not shown). *B. diazoefficiens* has eight terminal oxidases, namely, two *bd*-type oxidases and six heme-copper oxidases, the latter being further divided into two quinol oxidases and four cytochrome oxidases (Bühler et al. [2010](#)). Although the *ntrY* mutant has a defect in *cbb₃* expression and O₂ consumption, other oxidases can be used instead and the mutant is consequently able to grow under microoxic conditions. Following a similar methodological approach to the one used in this work, Torres et al. ([2013](#)) reported that an *E. meliloti fixN1* mutant defective in *cbb₃* oxidase synthesis showed a defect in TMPD-dependent oxidase activity when cells were incubated under microoxic conditions. Consequently, our results suggest that the decrease in TMPD-dependent oxidase activity observed in the *ntrY* mutant could be due to a decrease in *cbb₃* expression. In fact, under free-living microaerobic conditions, the FixP and FixO components of *cbb₃* oxidase were detected in both the WT and the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant, although the levels of these proteins were lower in the mutant. By contrast, the expression of the NapC component of Nap was similar in both the WT and the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant, suggesting that NtrY would not be involved in the expression of Nap in *B. diazoefficiens*. These results were also validated by qRT-PCR studies. An additional c-type cytochrome, CycM, was detected in microaerobically-grown cells. This cytochrome is an intermediate in the electron transfer between cytochrome *bc₁* and the *aa₃* oxidase (Delgado et al. [1998](#)). The lower expression of CycM in $\Delta ntrY$ mutant cells suggests that NtrY might be also involved in CycM expression. It has also been reported that CycM is not required for symbiotic N₂-fixation (Bott et al. [1991](#); Thöny-Meyer et al. [1989](#)).

In this work, the decreased capacity of the *B. diazoefficiens ntrY* mutant to consume O₂ under microaerobic conditions was also observed in bacteroids. It is well known that *cbb₃* oxidase is required in *B. diazoefficiens* bacteroids to support rhizobia respiration inside the nodules (Preisig et al. [1993](#)). Our chemiluminescence results indicated that the FixP and FixO components of *cbb₃* oxidase were undetectable in membranes of bacteroids produced by the $\Delta ntrY$ mutant. By contrast to free-living cells that have several terminal oxidases (Bühler et al. [2010](#)), in bacteroids the *cbb₃*-type is the sole oxidase required for symbiotic N₂-fixation (Preisig et al. [1993](#)). Consequently, the defect of *cbb₃* expression in $\Delta ntrY$ bacteroids explains the decreased capacity of the bacteroids induced by the *ntrY* mutant to respire and consequently fix N₂ efficiently. The involvement of *cbb₃* expression in symbiotic N fixation has been reported in *B. diazoefficiens* (Preisig et al. [1993](#)) as well as in *E. meliloti*, where a *fixN1* mutant defective in *cbb₃* expression showed a clear N fixation defect in alfalfa plants (Torres et al. [2013](#)). Furthermore, common bean plants inoculated with a *Rhizobium etli* strain having enhanced *cbb₃* oxidase expression in bacteroids reduced the sensitivity of symbiotic N₂-fixation to drought (Talbi et al. [2012](#)).

The $\Delta ntrY$ mutant exhibited a severe symbiotic phenotype since soybean plants inoculated with this mutant resulted small and with yellowish leaves, similarly to the uninoculated plants, and had a significant defect in nodule biomass. In addition, electron micrographs of $\Delta ntrY$ nodules showed symbiosomes with a low number of bacteroids per field and huge vacuolar structures, characteristic of cell lysis (Regensburger et al. 1986; Werner et al. 1984). Furthermore, SDWP, [N], ARA and Lb content results clearly demonstrated that NtrY was required for optimal N₂-fixation, since it is well known that these parameters are closely associated with the N₂-fixing capacity of legume root nodules (Dakora 1995). In contrast to our observations, other studies have reported that the NtrYX system was dispensable for symbiotic N₂ fixation in *E. meliloti* GR4 (Calatrava-Morales et al. 2017). Moreover, it has been described that only *ntrX* mutants from *E. meliloti* 1021 induced ineffective nodules with low nitrogenase activity in alfalfa plants (Wang et al. 2013). Therefore, our findings highlight that the role of the NtrYX system in N₂ fixation differs in *B. diazoefficiens* and *E. meliloti*, an observation that is not strange since these species are not closely related in evolutionary and taxonomical terms.

In agreement with our observations in *B. diazoefficiens*, NtrYX regulates the expression of the high-affinity cytochrome oxidase in *Brucella abortus* (Carrica et al. 2013). In this bacterium, NtrYX acts cooperatively with PrrBA as a global TCS that is sensitive to the cellular redox status. In turn, PrrBA controls the microaerobic expression of NtrY as well as the expression of the denitrification pathway in *B. abortus* (Carrica et al. 2013). Similarly, in *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* NtrX has a role in the regulation of respiratory gene expression by reducing the activity of cytochrome *cbb*₃ oxidase (Atack et al. 2013). In this case, the regulation of *cbb*₃ oxidase is also under the control of RegBA (Swem and Bauer 2002). RegBA/PrrBA are members of the family of the TCS regulatory systems present in a large number of proteobacteria, where they globally control gene expression mostly in a redox-responsive manner (Elsen et al. 2004; Wu and Bauer 2008). Moreover, Gregor et al. (2007) concluded that a direct interaction of RegA and NtrX in *R. capsulatus* connects the regulatory systems for redox and nitrogen control. In *B. diazoefficiens*, PrrBA, or its homologous RegBA, is named RegSR (Bauer et al. 1998). In contrast to *B. abortus* and *N. gonorrhoeae*, *fixNOQP* genes encoding the *cbb*₃ oxidase were not identified as RegR targets in a whole-genome transcription-profiling analysis of a *B. diazoefficiens* *regR* mutant grown under free-living oxic and microoxic conditions (Lindemann et al. 2007). Interestingly, in *B. diazoefficiens* FixK₂ is the master regulator involved in the control of the *fixNOQP* operon. The involvement of FixK₂ as a direct transcriptional regulator of *cbb*₃ oxidase has been demonstrated by using a transcriptomics approach (Mesa et al. 2008) and a FixK₂-dependent in vitro transcription assay (Mesa et al. 2005). This key regulator is part of the FixLJ-FixK₂ cascade linked to the RegSR-NifA regulatory cascade that co-ordinates the expression of genes required for N₂-fixation (Sciotti et al. 2003). NtrYX might participate in one or both regulatory cascades of *B. diazoefficiens*. However, transcriptomic and proteomic studies carried out under

oxic or microoxic conditions revealed no differences in the expression levels of *ntrY* or *ntrX* in *B. diazoefficiens* (Lindemann et al. [2007](#); Mesa et al. [2008](#); Pessi et al. [2007](#)). Further experiments are needed to elucidate the regulatory mechanism involved in the control of *B. diazoefficiens cbb₃* oxidase by this TCS. These studies will be considered in future investigations.

In conclusion, the results reported in this work revealed that *B. diazoefficiens* NtrYX TCS is required for adaptation to O₂ limitation inside the nodules. Furthermore, NtrYX plays an important role in cytochrome *cbb₃* expression and, consequently, in the establishment of an efficient symbiosis with soybean plants.

Abbreviations

CFU: Colony formation units

HK: Histidine kinase

Lb: leghaemoglobin

LB: Luria–Bertani medium

NDWP: Nodule dry weight per plant

NNP: Nodule number per plant

OD500: Optical density-500 nm

PPF: Photosynthetic Photon Flux

PSY: Peptone–salts–yeast extract

RR: Response regulator

SDWP: Shoot dry weight per plant

TCS: Two component system

TMPD: N,N,N',N'-tetramethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine

WT: Wild-type

YEM: Yeast-extract-mannitol medium

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